

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.4
Definizione parametri per programmi di calcolo automatico semplificati

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.4
Materialni parametri za programe za projektiranje

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.4 Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation programs

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Report 1.4

Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation programs

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.4 of the “PRO-SIS” project, concerning the “Definition of modelling details of masonry buildings for simplified software used by designers and calibration of parameters based on the studied analytical and numerical models”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

This REPORT 1.4 outlines the procedures to be used in commercial software for analysing the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings, considering the effects of reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques. Commonly used calculation tools are analysed: Midas GEN, 3MURI, PRO_SAP and SREMB, with each tool examined in its own section. Preliminary, a brief summary is presented concerning the behaviour and analysis of masonry buildings, along with the main challenges to be addressed when analysing reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques.

2. Overview of the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings

Most of the historic buildings in European cities and worldwide are made of brick or stone unreinforced masonry; this architectural heritage is variegated and ranges from Ancient Roman until Twentieth-century structures. Traditionally, masonry buildings were provided by wooden floors, and the presence of masonry arches and vaults was also rather frequent; however, in the most recent examples, floors made of steel joist with brick, of reinforced concrete vaults ceilings, of reinforced concrete joist with hollow brick interposed and of reinforced concrete plates were also employed.

These structures were built according to common practices, primarily based on empirical rules of proportion derived from experience. Although they typically perform well under normal operating conditions, they often exhibit high vulnerability in the event of a seismic occurrence, suffering serious damage and, in some cases, even collapsing. Therefore, ensuring adequate seismic behaviour for these buildings is a crucial to prevent loss of human lives, economic resources, and cultural and architectural heritage.

Ground motions caused by an earthquake induce three-dimensional vibrations in masonry buildings, resulting in vertical and horizontal inertial forces. Forces are transmitted from the intermediate floors and roof to the vertical masonry walls, and then to the foundation system. Typically, the seismic action is represented in a simplified way as a superposition of three load components: two acting horizontally in the main building's directions, and one vertically. In ordinary existing masonry buildings, the effects of the vertical component are usually negligible. The distribution of horizontal seismic loads among vertical resisting elements generally depends on their arrangement within the structure, their connections to each other, and the in-plane stiffness of the floors. Research ([1]-[2]) has shown that by ensuring structural regularity and effective connections between orthogonal walls and adequately rigid floor diaphragms (the so called "box behaviour" - Fig. 3.1.1), the distribution of seismic action among the resisting elements is primarily influenced by their stiffness. This allows for the effective use of the in-plane resistance of masonry walls oriented in the seismic direction, thus limiting out-of-plane forces on other walls. Conversely, if structural integrity is inadequate, walls may behave independently, both in-plane and out-of-plane, leading to partial collapses from local mechanisms such as wall overturning, vertical or horizontal bending, corner overturning, or gable collapse. Additionally, dangerous torsional vibrations can occur when there is an unbalanced distribution of masonry resisting elements in plan or height.

Fig. 3.1.1 Structural behaviour of masonry buildings: (a) schematization of "box behaviour", which promotes the desirable activation of (b) the in-plane response of masonry walls, while avoiding the activation of (c) weaker out-of-plane response

Besides structural integrity and distribution of resisting elements, the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings is strictly related to the mechanical characteristics of masonry itself. In fact, despite of its appreciable resistance when subjected to compression, masonry has a very low tensile resistance [3]. This mechanical characteristic, usually related to the scarce consistency of mortar joints and of the mortar-units interface, governs the main failure mechanisms in masonry resisting elements, both in-plane and out-of-plane. Moreover, the presence of multiple-leaf masonry walls without effective connections among leaves is also rather frequent; this aspect further weakens the resistance and stiffness characteristics of masonry walls.

A proper knowledge of the building structural characteristics and of the masonry consistency is thus necessary. Moreover, to ensure the seismic safety of existing masonry buildings, it is essential to apply reliable procedures for assessing their actual structural performances and, if needed, for designing effective intervention strategies.

Based on evidence from past-earthquakes, distinct macro-elements are typically identified in perforated walls, when studying the global behaviour of masonry buildings: piers and spandrels (Fig. 3.1.2). A pier is defined as the masonry portion between two horizontally adjacent openings or between an opening and a building corner, while a spandrel is the masonry portion between two vertically adjacent openings or between an opening and the roof. Referring to in-plane loads, masonry piers are subjected to axial compressive stress, shear forces and bending moments; the spandrels, coupling vertical resistant elements, are subject to shear forces and bending moments but, typically, only to very limited compressive forces.

Fig. 3.1.2 Identification of pier and spandrels in a perforated masonry wall

Experience has evidenced that the in-plane failure of a pier or a spandrel may be due to diagonal cracking, bending (rocking and/or toe crushing) or sliding, depending on the wall slenderness, axial stress level and boundary conditions, as well as masonry characteristics [4]. Shear-dominated response exhibited diagonal cracking (Fig. 3.1.3a,c) and a load-drift response characterized by high energy dissipation, but by rather rapid strength degradation. In the flexure-dominated response, the damage is typically concentrated at the extremities (Fig. 3.1.3b,d); it is characterized by a very moderate dissipation of hysteretic energy but a rather smooth strength degradation. Sliding may occur in piers combined with rocking, in case of low axial loads and regular, smooth bed joints; sliding failure at spandrel extremities is unlikely in periodic masonry, as the mortar joints are not continuous along the vertical direction. Due to

the negligible axial stress, spandrels typically exhibit a very limited bending resistance; the presence of effective horizontal tie beams at floor levels (e.g. steel rods, r.c. beams) counteracts this mechanism, leading to a shear-dominated failure.

Analytical correlations to evaluate the resistance of masonry piers and spandrels, based on the different, possible failure mechanisms, along with the respective ultimate drift limits, are available in the literature and have also been adopted in different national and international building codes and guidelines. Further details and examples of application can be found in the "PRO-SIS" Report 1.1 [5].

Fig. 3.1.3 Typical failure mechanisms of masonry piers and spandrels: (a, c) diagonal cracking, (b, d) bending with rocking and/or toe crushing

For the global analysis of masonry buildings, simplified modelling methods that subdivide masonry walls into macro-elements have been developed. Nonlinear static analyses (pushover) based on macro-element modelling have proven to be a useful, reliable tool for obtaining a realistic prediction of the resistance and displacement capacities with relatively low computational effort, provided that there is proper calibration of the mechanical parameters and a thoughtful schematization of the resisting elements.

The simplified macro-elements models represent an evolution of the well-known POR approach [6]. In simplified macro-elements models [7]-[9], the resisting elements (i.e. the piers and the spandrels), are usually schematised by means mono-dimensional, elastic beam elements, connected by rigid beams, defining the "Equivalent Frame" model of the structure (Appendix A). The nonlinear response is lumped into localized hinges, whose resistance and displacement capacities are determined by applying the simplified analytical correlations. However, different macro-element schematizations (e.g. based on bi-dimensional elements [10]) are also available.

3. Analysis of CRM strengthened masonry structures

The strengthening technique for masonry structures primarily addressed in the "CONSTRAIN" project is the Composite Reinforced Mortar - CRM technique. It consists in the application, on the masonry surface (one or both sides), of a 30 mm thick mortar coating with preformed Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer composite meshes embedded, in combination with the introduction of transversal connectors.

CRM was proved beneficial for the performances of masonry elements, improving resistance, displacement capacities and energy dissipation. As broadly discussed in the "PRO-SIS" Report 1.1 [5], the CRM application can modify the failure mechanism of the masonry element and its effectiveness may vary, depending on the governing failure mechanism, as well as the characteristics of the masonry. The analytical-mechanical models capable of describing the behaviour of CRM strengthened masonry piers and spandrels, based on experimental evidence, are outlined in [5].

However, conventional strategies/procedures necessitate to be developed to account for these improvements when performing the global numerical analysis of masonry buildings by using common commercial software. The application of the macro-element modelling approach described for unreinforced masonry in §2 is likely suitable also for CRM strengthened masonry, but some adjustments are deemed.

Some commonly used calculation tools are analysed: Midas GEN, 3MURI, PRO_SAP and SREMB.

3.1. Analyses with Midas GEN

The software Midas GEN, v1.3 (CSP FEA Engineering Solutions) [11] as used for the numerical simulation.

3.1.1. Modelling overview

The software Midas GEN allows to carry out nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for masonry buildings. The modelling of the structure is based on the “Equivalent frame” model with lumped plasticity (Appendix A). The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the geometry of the equivalent frame;
- the vertical loads;
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- the behaviour of the lumped plasticity hinges.

- Geometry

The user models the masonry structure according to the “Equivalent Frame” method (Fig. 3.1.1), by using beam elements, and provides the effective lengths of the piers and spandrels and of the “rigid nodes” (Appendix A). The rigid beams forming the “rigid nodes” of the structure can be modelled separately from pier/spandrel elements or by defining beam-end-offset constraints applied on piers/spandrel elements. Anyway, the user must be careful in assigning the self-weights of such rigid portions, to avoid double counting. An effective strategy is, for example, to apply the beam-end offset constraints option to vertical elements (therefore, having the masonry self-weight) in combination with a separate modelling of the horizontal rigid elements (assigning them zero self-weight).

The user also defines the beams cross sections (bending deformation is always considered, the shear one is optional but is activated by default). For the proper assignment of the plastic capacities, the Y-local axis of the beam has to be arranged along the wall thickness (i.e. perpendicular to the wall plane).

The piers of the ground floor are typically fixed at the base. To properly apply floor diaphragm constraints, the user shall keep attention in constraining only the nodes at the top of the piers, keeping free all the other nodes at that level.

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads transmitted by the floors can be assigned manually as nodal or distributed loads. The “assign floor load” option allows also automatic assignment, once floor typology (i.e. one/two way) and the nodes of the loading area are selected.

The masonry self-weights (defined in the material properties) shall also be activated.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the basic masonry mechanical characteristics in terms of self-weight, Young’s modulus, and shear modulus (or Poisson’s ratio).

- Lumped plasticity features

The user selects the type of masonry element (pier or spandrel) and defines the non-linear masonry characteristics:

- for the piers: the shear strength (τ_0), the vertical compressive strength (f_m), and the vertical stress distribution coefficient (0.85 by default);
- for the spandrels: the shear strength (τ_0), the horizontal compressive strength ($f_{m,h}$) and the horizontal tie resistance (H_p).

The hinges to be activated for the pushover analysis of masonry buildings are, typically, in-plane shear, at the beam centre (Fz), and in-plane bending (My), at both beam ends. Axial compression can also be activated (Fx).

The user is asked also to select the strength formulations: for the purposes of this study, "existing masonry" and "irregular masonry type" options are suggested. Thus:

- for pier elements, the shear resistance ($V_{P,d(URM)}$) and the bending resistance ($M_{P(URM)}$) are determined through Eqs. 3.1 and 3.2, respectively:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b_P \cdot t_P \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$M_{P(URM)} = \frac{\sigma_0 b_P^2 t_P}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{0.85 \cdot f_m} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

- for spandrel elements, the shear resistance ($V_{S,d(URM)}$) and the bending resistance ($M_{S(URM)}$) are determined through Eqs. 3.3 and 3.4, respectively.

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b_S \cdot t_S \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$M_{S(URM)} = \frac{H_p b_S}{2} \left(1 - \frac{H_p}{0.85 f_{m,h} \cdot h_S \cdot t_S} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

- t_P masonry pier thickness
- b_P masonry pier width
- l_P masonry pier height (i.e. "effective length")
- t_S masonry spandrel thickness
- b_S masonry spandrel height
- l_S masonry spandrel length (i.e. "effective length")
- σ_0 mean compressive stress on the pier/spandrel
- f_m masonry vertical compressive strength
- $f_{m,h}$ masonry horizontal compressive strength
- τ_0 equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$
- β pier/spandrel slenderness factor ($1.0 \leq \beta = l/b \leq 1.5$)
- H_p tensile resistance of the horizontal tie (however, limited to $0.4 \cdot f_{m,h} \cdot b_S \cdot t_S$)

Basically, for the in-plane shear mechanism the software considers the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12]. For in-plane bending mechanism of piers, it accounts only for the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads. For the strength in-plane bending mechanism of spandrels, it assumes the presence of an effective horizontal tie, otherwise the resistance is null.

Although, spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, even though small, due to the interaction between adjacent blocks at the spandrel ends, as evidenced also from the experimental "CONSTRAIN" tests on the unstrengthened spandrel samples [5]. Thus, in this case, the user shall "force" the software for a proper evaluation of the bending resistance. For example, a fictitious horizontal tie resistance ($H_{p,fit}$) can be set, based on the actual resistance expected for the spandrel (as detailed in [5]).

For each hinge type, the user defines the post-elastic behaviour (FEMA type - Fig. 3.1.2). Point "B" is automatically determined (based on the elastic stiffness of the element and the resistance). The user defines "C", "D" and "E" (in terms of both strength ratio, in respect to point "B", and deformation capacities) and can opt/opt out for the total strength loss at the reaching of point "E" (kept constant by default).

Based on the provided hinges properties, the software automatically calculates the lateral strength and displacement capacities of masonry piers and spandrels; the axial stress level is automatically updated at each analysis step. The software considers the mean axial stress in the element to determine the resistance of hinges.

Fig. 3.1.1 "Equivalent frame" model schematization

Fig. 3.1.2 Plastic hinge behaviour according to FEMA 356 [13]

3.1.2. Analysis features

The user sets up the pushover analysis under displacement control (of a master node, i.e. the mass centre at the roof level), specifying the lateral load pattern, the target displacement, and the number of steps. The vertical loads shall be preliminary applied.

Different lateral load patterns can be applied: proportional to a static load case defined by the user, uniform acceleration (proportional to the mass at each story level), proportional to a mode shape, normalized mode shape times mass (the load pattern for the pushover analysis is derived by multiplying the normalized mode shape by the mass). The last three types require eigenvalue analysis to be previously performed; to that, it is essential to define the masses of the structure (e.g. the self-weights and added loads can be converted into masses). After the analysis, the user can check the calculated strength of each inelastic hinge at each step.

3.1.3. How to account for CRM

As previously specified, the software performs the pushover analysis by automatically evaluating the in-plane resistance and displacement characteristics of the piers and spandrels, by automatically applying the analytical correlations presented in §3.1.1, that are suitable for URM. Currently, the software does not include an automatic procedure to account for the CRM contribution. Thus, for CRM strengthened masonry, the user shall “force” the software by providing “fictitious” equivalent masonry properties, to account also for the CRM reinforcement contribution. In fact, the software does not allow to modify the correlations for the resistance estimation, but just the masonry material parameters and plastic hinges drift limits.

For CRM strengthened elements (both piers and spandrels), the “spandrel element type” shall be selected in the software and equivalent material parameters values $\tau_{0,eq}$ (masonry shear strength) and $H_{P,eq}$ must be set, according to Eqs. 3.5 and 3.6:

$$\tau_{0,eq} = \frac{\sigma_0}{3} + \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_0^2}{9} + \left(\frac{\beta \cdot V_{d(CRM)}}{1.5 \cdot b \cdot t}\right)^2} \quad (3.5)$$

$$H_{P,eq} = \frac{2 \cdot M_{(CRM)}}{b} \quad (3.6)$$

where:

$V_{d(CRM)}$ Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in shear (related to the in-plane diagonal cracking mechanism)

M_{CRM} Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in bending (related to the in-plane bending mechanism)

The values of $V_{d(CRM)}$ and M_{CRM} shall be calculated analytically by the user, applying the correlations provided in the “PRO-SIS” Report 1.1 [5] for CRM. Note also that the masonry compressive strength shall be set fictitiously to a high value (e.g. 1000 MPa). For spandrel elements, it is assumed $\sigma_0 = 0$ in Eq. (3.5). Also increased ultimate drift values must be assigned to CRM strengthened masonry elements [5].

3.1.4. Validation

For the validation of the procedure, two benchmark examples (a pier and a spandrel element) are considered, and the comparison between numerical simulations and analytical calculations are made. The reference to the analytical calculations is provided in the Appendix B.

For piers, the vertical axial compression is simulated by applying a vertical force to the upper node and the pushover analysis is performed by gradually increasing lateral displacement of the upper node. The plotted graphs represent the base shear, F_p , varying the net horizontal displacement d_h between the top and the bottom of the effective pier length l_{eff} .

For spandrels, the pushover analysis is performed by gradually increasing the nodal rotation at the two base supports while controlling the horizontal displacement of the node at the top-right node. The plotted graphs represent the shear acting on the spandrel, F_s , against the distortion (i.e. net displacement d_v between the spandrel ends, determined orthogonally in respect to the direction of the adjacent rigid parts).

In both cases, the self-weight is not considered.

Fig. 3.1.3 Schematization of the validation numerical models for the pier, according to (a) a shear-type or (b) a cantilever beam scheme, and for the spandrel

It is observed that for both piers and spandrels, the analytical and numerical predictions coincide, in terms both of capacity curves and failure mode. It is thus concluded that the adopted procedure allows the software to correctly reproduce in a simplified way the behaviour of both unstrengthened and CRM strengthened masonry.

ID:	URM_Pier_st_0.3	R1_Pier_st_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=135.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.232\text{MPa}$)	R2_Pier_st_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=180.2\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.382\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	1.31 mm 50.5 kN	1.20 mm 90.3 kN	1.10 mm 120.0 kN
Collapse:	9.38 mm 50.5 kN	37.5 mm 90.4 kN	37.5 mm 120.1 kN
Failure mode:	Diagonal cracking	Bending	Bending

ID:	URM_Pier_ct_0.3	R1_Pier_ct_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=135.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.232\text{MPa}$)	R2_Pier_ct_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=180.2\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.382\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	1.53 mm 22.2 kN	1.35 mm 35.8 kN	1.20 mm 47.5 kN
Collapse:	18.7 mm 22.2 kN	37.5 mm 35.8 kN	37.5 mm 47.6 kN
Failure mode:	Bending	Bending	Bending

ID:	URM_Spandrel	R1_Spandrel ($H_{p,eq}=72.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.209\text{MPa}$)	R2_Spandrel ($H_{p,eq}=73.8\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.364\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
H_p	100 kN	100 kN	100 kN
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	0.55 mm 18.0 kN	0.72 mm 41.8 kN	0.76 mm 49.2 kN
Collapse:	17.8 mm 10.8 kN	36.0 mm 41.8 kN	36.1 mm 49.2 kN
Failure mode:	Diagonal cracking	Diagonal cracking	Bending

3.2. Analyses with 3MURI

The numerical simulation was conducted using 3Muri software (version 12.6.2.4) [14], developed by S.T.A. DATA. 3Muri provides an integrated and modular solution for analysing masonry and mixed structures. It employs a macro-element-based approach, schematizing the structure as an assembly of macro-elements to replicate the mechanical behavior of the walls. This approach allows for both rapid and detailed analysis.

3.2.1. *Modelling overview*

The software 3Muri allows to conduct nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for masonry buildings. The modelling of the structure is based on the “Equivalent frame” model with lumped plasticity (Appendix A). The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the geometry of the structure, from which the equivalent frame model is automatically generated. The geometry can also be imported from various file formats (e.g., DXF, IFC, and other supported formats);
- the vertical loads;
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- the behaviour of the lumped plasticity hinges.

- Geometry

The automatically generated frame model schematizes the structure into piers and spandrels (Fig. 3.2.1). The user can later modify these elements to consider a different schematization, if needed.

Fig. 3.2.1 “Equivalent frame” model schematization: (a) 3D representation of the input geometry; (b) extruded view of the macro elements

- Material properties and lumped plasticity features

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the following masonry mechanical characteristics, according to the example in Fig. 3.2.2:

- self-weight (w);
- Young's modulus (E);
- shear modulus (G).
- vertical compressive strength (f_m);
- equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (τ_0);
- confidence factor (FC);
- material strength partial safety factor (γ_m);
- shear and bending limit drifts;
- type of formulation considered (existing masonry is herein considered).

These properties can be assigned to the walls or to each element individually.

Name	PRO-SIS Pilot01
E [N/mm ²]	1.500,00
G [N/mm ²]	500,00
w [kN/m ³]	18
f _m [N/cm ²]	345,00
f _k [N/cm ²]	345,00
τ [N/cm ²]	9,00
f _{vlim} [N/mm ²]	0,0
FC	1,00
γ _m	1,00
Shear drift	0,0050
Bending drift	0,0100
φ _∞	0,0
Damage condition	Existing
Description	for parametric study
Library	

Fig. 3.2.2 Input form for unreinforced masonry material data

The user considers the strength formulation for “existing” masonry and selects the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12] for the shear resistance (Eq. 3.1 for piers and Eq. 3.3 for spandrels), while the bending resistance of piers is determined using Eq. 3.2. For spandrels with a horizontal tie, the tie material properties and diameter, and its position are inputted in the wall segment attributes (Fig. 3.2.3). The software then uses Eq. 3.4 to calculate the spandrel's strength.

Based on the provided macro-elements properties, the software automatically calculates the lateral strength and displacement capacities of masonry piers and spandrels; the axial stress level is automatically updated at each analysis step.

Fig. 3.2.3 Input form for masonry section properties data

Since spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, although reduced, it can be accounted e.g. by inserting a fictitious horizontal tie resistance corresponding to the expected resistance.

3.2.2. Analysis features

The user sets up the pushover analysis under displacement control (of a master node, i.e. the mass centre at the roof level), specifying the lateral load pattern, the target displacement, and the number of steps. The vertical loads shall be preliminary applied. There are different lateral load distribution options, including uniform acceleration and proportional to static forces.

The pushover procedure consists of an incremental static analysis with displacement control at only one degree of freedom, maintaining constant ratios between the applied forces. The capacity curve, which plots the total base shear against the horizontal displacement, represents the structure's behavior under horizontal loads (Fig. 3.2.4); the damage state of the elements is also given.

Fig. 3.2.4 Pushover analysis results: (a) capacity curve and (b) element damage state

3.2.3. How to account for CRM

The 3Muri software includes the possibility of automatic calculation of the FRCM reinforcement contribution, by applying the formulations given in the CNR-DT 215/2018 technical document [15].

This option can also be useful to consider the contribution of the CRM, with the necessary precautions. In particular, “user defined” parameters shall be set for the reinforcement properties, specifying the equivalent thickness/area, Young’s modulus and ultimate drift for the fibres in the two main directions (Fig. 3.2.5).

It is important to clarify that the equivalent thickness/area of fibres is that at one side of the wall. Then the user can specify whether the reinforcement is applied to one or both sides.

However, it is observed that when the one-side application option is selected, a reduction in the shear contribution of the reinforcement will automatically be applied by the software, complying with CNR-DT 215/2018 [15]. A way to avoid this reduction is selecting the double side application option and set halved values for the thickness/area (Fig. 3.2.6).

In the interface, also the new shear and bending ultimate drifts of the strengthened elements must be specified; although also the drift limits for plain masonry must be updated with the increased values (Fig. 3.2.7). It is observed that the specified drifts apply equally to both piers and spandrels; thus, if different drift values are to be assigned, it is necessary to define different masonry and reinforcement types.

Two sides CRM

Material properties

Type	Name
Name	MuraturaB1 con CRM_R2
Material colour	
Texture	
E [N/mm ²]	3900
Eh [N/mm ²]	3900
G [N/mm ²]	1430

Define characteristics

Masonry panel Masonry panel + R.C. tie beam

R.C. wall R.C. beam Steel/w

Masonry panel

Material

MuraturaB1 con CRM_R2

Reinforced masonry/Reinforcement

ConstrainCRM (MasonryB1)

Piers

Reinforcement properties

Name: ConstrainCRM Reinforcement type: **FRCM** User defined Use conventional values

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		y f,d	
ηa definition		α	
Exposure class		y m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0100
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0200
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.058	tf [mm]	0.058
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear+Bending	Effect typology	Shear+Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
ηa		ηa	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]		ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000	ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00
		Summit edging	
		Number of layers	0
		Width bf [mm]	0.000
		tf [mm]	0.000

Spandrels

Reinforcement properties

Name: ConstrainCRM Reinforcement type: **FRCM** User defined Use conventional values

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		y f,d	
ηa definition		α	
Exposure class		y m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0300
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0300
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.058	tf [mm]	0.058
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear+Bending	Effect typology	Shear+Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
ηa		ηa	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]		ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000	ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00
		Summit edging	
		Number of layers	0
		Width bf [mm]	0.000
		tf [mm]	0.000

Fig. 3.2.5 Input form for the definition of CRM parameters (application at both sides)

One side CRM

Material properties

Type: **lName**

Name: **MasonryB1 with CRM_R1**

Material colour:

Texture:

E [N/mm ²]	2700
Eh [N/mm ²]	2700
G [N/mm ²]	980

Define characteristics

Masonry panel | Masonry panel + R.C. tie beam

R.C. wall | R.C. beam | Steel/h

Masonry panel

Material: **MuraturaB1 con CRM_R1**

Reinforced masonry/Reinforcement

ConstrainCRM (MasonryB1)

Piers

Reinforcement properties

Name: **ConstrainCRM** | Reinforcement type: **FRCM** | User defined

Masonry	
Masonry type	
na definition	
Exposure class	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]	
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]	
Dist. application [mm]	

Pier	
Layout	Continue
bf [mm]	
Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious
na	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Calculation coefficients	
γ _{f,d}	
α	
γ _m	
Shear drift	0.0100
Bending drift	0.0200
β	0.79

Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue
bf [mm]	
Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious
na	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Spandrels

Reinforcement properties

Name: **ConstrainCRM** | Reinforcement type: **FRCM** | User defined

Masonry	
Masonry type	
na definition	
Exposure class	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]	
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]	
Dist. application [mm]	

Pier	
Layout	Continue
bf [mm]	
Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious
na	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Calculation coefficients	
γ _{f,d}	
α	
γ _m	
Shear drift	0.0300
Bending drift	0.0300
β	0.79

Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue
bf [mm]	
Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious
na	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Fig. 3.2.6 Input form for the definition of CRM parameters (application at one side)

Shear drift	0,0100	Shear drift	0,0100	Shear drift	0,0300
Bending drift	0,0200	Bending drift	0,0200	Bending drift	0,0300

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3.2.7 Input drift values in the material data form for strengthened masonry piers: (a) strengthened on one side; (b) strengthened on two sides and (c) drift values for CRM strengthened spandrels on one- and two-sides

3.3. Analyses with PRO_SAP

The software PRO_SAP v. 24.10.0 (2S.l. Software e Servizi per l'Ingegneria S.r.l.) [16] was used for the numerical simulation, combined with the PRO_SAM [17] application to generate the equivalent frame model (Appendix A).

3.3.1. *Modelling overview*

The software PRO_SAP allows to carry out nonlinear static analysis (pushover) for masonry buildings, by adopting the equivalent frame model. The structure modelling starts from the definition of the masonry properties, analysis criteria, and geometry. The user can use a wizard where it is possible to define the 2D dimensions of walls with openings, from which the equivalent frame is created by the algorithm. The behavior of lumped plasticity hinges is defined automatically by the software, based on Italian code indications.

The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the masonry mechanical properties (material);
- the masonry design criteria;
- the geometry of the equivalent frame;
- the vertical loads.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user can assign Young's modulus, shear modulus (or Poisson's ratio), vertical compressive strength, horizontal compressive strength, shear strength (for diagonal failure), self-weight.

In Fig. 3.1.1 an example of the interface for defining the masonry characteristics is illustrated: by selecting an existing material, the software automatically defines an orthotropic material with equal mechanical characteristics in the three main directions.

Stringa identificativa		PRO SIS
Generalità		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Materiale esistente		
Fattore di confidenza FC m		0.0
Resistenze		
Resistenza fm		3.45 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fhm		1.725 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fv0m		9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fv0hm		9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza tau0m		9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fvlimm		0.0 [N/mm ²]
Coefficiente mu tilda		0.4
Coefficiente fi		0.5
Resistenza fbN		4.16 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbm		0.0 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbhm		0.0 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbtm		0.0 [N/mm ²]
Setta i valori non introdotti (...)		setta i valori = 0
<input type="checkbox"/> Elasto-plastico per aste ...		
<input type="checkbox"/> Muratura consolidata		
Proprietà		
Peso specifico		0.0 [N/mm ³]
Dilatazione termica		1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Dilatazione termica 2		1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Dilatazione termica 3		1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Smorzamento		5.0
Costanti elastiche		
Modulo E		1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Poisson		0.0
Modulo G		500.0 [N/mm ²]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ortotropo		
Costanti elastiche ortotropo		
Modulo E2		1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Modulo E3		1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Poisson 1-3		0.0
Poisson 2-3		0.0
Modulo G1-3		500.0 [N/mm ²]
Modulo G2-3		500.0 [N/mm ²]
Avanzate		
Stringa identificativa		

Fig. 3.3.1 Example of the screen for defining the masonry characteristics

- Design criteria

Resistance and displacement capacities for the masonry elements (piers and spandrels) are determined by the software. Design criteria are selected by the user within those included in the software database (Fig. 3.3.2). For this study, according with the common assumptions made for the other software, the "NTC criteria" was selected (complying with the Italian building code and its commentary, [18]-[19]).

For the diagonal cracking failure mechanism, the Turnšek-Čačovič model [12] is considered for both piers and spandrels. The standard in-plane bending failure mechanism is also accounted by default, depending on the masonry compressive strength and on the axial stress level (for piers) or on the horizontal tie resistance (for spandrels). Default ultimate drift values for piers and spandrels are those given by the code; however, the user can modify them.

Design criteria table	
R.C. Walls	R.C. slabs
Floors and panels	Steel truss
<input type="checkbox"/> Apply par. C4.5.6.2	Reinforced concrete beams
<input type="checkbox"/> Apply EC6 app. C	Steel columns
Tie strength	Steel beams
Shear failure M	Masonry
Shear failure F	Timber
<input type="checkbox"/> Sliding [7.8.3] - (MC)	XLAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Diagonal crack [C8.7.1.16] (TC)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Diagonal crack [C8.7.1.17] (MM)	
Reinforcement and other advanced parameters...	
Masonry wall	
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only	
Drift DLS	2.0000e-03
Drift M	1.0000e-02
Drift V	5.0000e-03
Masonry Spandrel	
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only M	
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only V	
Plasticity factor	1.0
Drift M	2.0000e-02
Drift ini V	5.0000e-03
Drift fin V	5.0000e-03

Fig. 3.3.2 Example of definition of design criteria

- Geometry

When using the PRO_SAM application, the user must define the plane geometry of each wall (perimeter). The start and end points of the wall in the horizontal direction can be defined either by coordinates or by a click on the specific points; the wall's height is defined last (Fig. 3.3.3a). Similarly, for defining the openings, it is necessary to indicate the start and end points in the horizontal direction, and the height of the spandrels below and above the openings. Then, the automatic process creates the equivalent frame, as a combination of piers, spandrels and rigid elements (Fig. 3.3.3b). However, the user can adjust the length of the rigid elements.

Fig. 3.3.3 Example of wall geometry definition (a) and equivalent frame generation (b)

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads, due to floors, can be assigned by giving the floor load, area, and orientation or by a nodal force acting at the top of each pier.

- Lumped plasticity features

The assignment of lumped plasticity hinges is done by the software, which automatically identifies piers and spandrels, and assigns the plasticity law accordingly to the selected design criteria. Typically, a rigid-plastic behavior is assigned to the lumped plastic hinges. Coherently with the selected "NTC design criteria" described above, the resistance value, for each element, is defined as indicated in the following:

- for piers, Eq. 3.1 and Eq. 3.2 applies for the shear and bending resistance, respectively;
- for the spandrels, the bending resistance follows Eq. 3.4, while the shear is according to Eq. 3.7:

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \tau_0 \cdot b_S \cdot t_S \quad (3.7)$$

Where:

- t_S masonry spandrel thickness
- b_S masonry spandrel height
- τ_0 equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$

It is observed that, differently from the piers, the formulation for the shear resistance of the spandrels does not consider the slenderness factor β . If the user wishes to consider it, it will be necessary to insert, for the spandrel masonry material properties, an actual shear resistance value scaled by $1.5/\beta$.

Moreover, for the in-plane bending resistance of spandrels, the software assumes the presence of an effective horizontal tie, otherwise the resistance is null. But spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, although reduced, thanks to the block-to-block interaction at the spandrel ends. Thus, in this case, if the user wishes to account it, the software can be "forced" by inserting a fictitious horizontal tie resistance.

3.3.2. Analysis features

The software selects the control point (master node) in the mass centre of the top floor.

The vertical loads are preliminary applied; then the horizontal displacement of the control point is applied incrementally, according to the assigned lateral load pattern. Different lateral load patterns can be applied. For the scope of this study, a triangular distribution proportional to the static forces is considered (Fig. 3.3.4). The user can set the number of steps in which the software applies the incremental displacement.

After the analysis, the global capacity curve (lateral force vs. displacement of the control point) is provided (Fig. 3.3.5). The user is also able to check the failure mode of each element and the calculated strength of each inelastic hinge at each step.

Fig. 3.3.4 Example of setting analysis parameters

Fig. 3.3.5 Example of output (capacity curve and failure mode of elements)

3.3.3. How to account for CRM

The PRO SAP software (combined with the PRO_SAM application) includes the possibility of automatic calculation of an FRCM reinforcement contribution by applying the formulations given in the CNR-DT 215/2018 technical document [15]. This option is easy to adapt to the purposes of this project.

Where the strengthening intervention is applied, a new material must be defined (Fig. 3.3.6). After that, the FRCM application must be selected; however, the “simplified method” option (based on amplifications coefficients) must not be selected.

Fig. 3.3.6 Example of the interface for defining the CRM strengthened masonry characteristics

The user must define the properties of the CRM strengthening systems, specifying the equivalent thickness, Young's modulus, limit strength and strain of fibres (Fig. 3.3.7).

Two different CRM applications are considered in this project: single- and double-sided. It is observed that, according to CNR DT 215/2018, in case of one-side application the shear contribution of the reinforcement is reduced by 30%. To avoid that, according to experimental evidence, a fictitious property for the one-side application was adopted, where a two-side application was considered in the software, but assuming a halved thickness (Fig. 3.3.7).

ID	ID	Thickness	single side	E	sig u (composite)	eps u, f %	eps lim, c %	Direction	Exposition	Fiber	eta o	alfa internal	alfa terminal	H bands width	H bands pitch	V bands wid.	V bands pitch	uncovered area	Use ONLY for c
n. 1	R1	0.06	NO	72702.00	1345.00	1.85	1.85	biaxial	internal	glass	0.90	1.00	1.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	0.00	NO
n. 3	R2	0.12	NO	72702.00	1345.00	1.85	1.85	biaxial	internal	glass	0.90	1.00	1.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	0.00	NO

Fig. 3.3.7 CRM reinforcement properties

To consider the stiffness increase due to the CRM application (related to the mortar coating), higher values of Young's and shear moduli must be assigned to the reinforced masonry

material (based on the masonry and plaster moduli, weighted on their respective thickness). Similarly, also the self-weight can be adjusted; however, the increase is very limited. To consider the benefits of the CRM system in terms of ultimate drifts on piers and spandrels, the “design criteria” also needs to be modified (Fig. 3.3.8).

Fig. 3.3.8 Update design criteria for CRM strengthened masonry

3.4. Analyses with SREMB

3.4.1. Modelling overview

The software SREMB (internal prototype software of ZRMK; similar to the POR method [6]) allows to carry out nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for the critical story of a masonry building. Usually that is the ground floor, but the procedure can be repeated for all the stories, to determine the weakest. The modelling of the story is based on the subdivision in pier macro elements.

The user is asked to define:

- the geometry of the macro elements (walls, piers);
- the vertical loads (stresses due to vertical loads on macro elements);
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- parameters for calculation.

The following assumptions are considered in the seismic analysis:

- masonry piers are considered connected at story levels with the floor structures, which are stiff in their plane. This assumption ensures the participation of all walls in resisting the horizontal load;

- the walls are clamped at the upper and lower edges into the ceiling structure, into the lintel / parapet part of the wall;
- cantilever type boundary condition is generally assumed for the piers in single storey structures and in the top story of multi-story buildings. The presence of reinforced concrete beams, strong (tall) spandrels or stiff masonry in the above storey can be considered by assuming symmetrical boundary condition (shear-type);
- the walls of composite cross-sections (L, T, H) are considered as the sum of the walls separated from each other by vertical joints;
- the contribution of the resistance of the walls to the resistance of the floor depends on their stiffness and load-bearing capacity, as well as on their deformation, which depends mainly on their location in the building plan (accounting for eccentric effects);
- walls transmit their share of the horizontal load even in the nonlinear range, but only until their deformations exceed the deformations at the failure limit (defined by the masonry's ductility for the considered failure mechanism).

- Geometry

The user models the masonry structure as macro elements (walls, piers) for each storey separately. The rigid horizontal ties (reinforced concrete beams or steel ties) are assumed to guarantee a box like behaviour where all walls contribute to the storey load bearing capacity. The distribution of seismic action among the resisting elements (walls) is according to their stiffness and is limited by their load bearing capacity (considering both strength and deformation). The out of plane behaviour is not considered in the analysis. Also, spandrels are assumed to be perfectly rigid.

Macro elements are usually symmetrically fixed into the structure except at the top floor, where a cantilever boundary condition is considered to determine the stiffness and strength of the piers.

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads transmitted by the floors (including masonry self-weight) must be assigned manually as vertical loads on macro elements.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the basic masonry mechanical characteristics in terms of Young's modulus and shear modulus, compressive strength, and referential diagonal tensile strength (approx., 1.5 times the shear strength) .

The designer prepares the geometry and the material data (Fig. 3.4.1) in an Excel file.

n	dx [m]	dy [m]	x [m]	y [m]	sig.o [MPa]	h_x [m]	h_y [m]	boudary
Pilot PRO-SIS_01								
9								
1	1,050	0,250	0,525	0,175	0,130	2,22	3	1
2	1,250	0,250	2,875	0,175	0,220	1,4	3	1
3	1,050	0,250	5,225	0,175	0,130	2,22	3	1
4	1,050	0,250	0,525	4,175	0,140	2,22	3	1
5	1,250	0,250	2,875	4,175	0,220	1,4	3	1
6	1,050	0,250	5,225	4,175	0,140	2,22	3	1
7	0,250	4,350	0,175	2,175	0,100	3	3	1
8	0,250	1,400	5,575	0,875	0,130	3	1,4	1
9	0,250	1,750	5,575	3,300	0,130	3	1,4	1

n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)	način	E [MPa]	G [MPa]	fc [MPa]	ft [MPa]	du.s [-]	du.f [-]
Pilot_01								
9								
1	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
2	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
3	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
4	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005

Fig. 3.4.1 Input for definition of geometry and material data

3.4.2. Analysis features

The storey hysteresis envelope is the sum of the hysteresis envelopes of the walls that constitute the storey. The behaviour of individual walls under horizontal loads is an idealized elastoplastic hysteresis envelope, which is determined by the initial effective stiffness of the wall, its load-bearing capacity, and the ductility factor that limits the deformation of the wall in the inelastic range. The total storey horizontal force is distributed to the walls in proportion to their stiffnesses. The lower between the bending and shear load-bearing capacity is considered for determining the deformation at the elastic limit. The elastic stiffness of an individual wall is calculated using Eq. 3.8.

$$K_e = \frac{G \cdot A_w}{1.2 \cdot h \cdot \left[1 + \frac{G}{c \cdot E} \left(\frac{h}{l} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (3.8)$$

where:

- l masonry pier width
- h masonry pier height (i.e. "effective length")
- A_w wall horizontal cross section ($l \cdot t$)
- E elastic modulus of masonry (initial)
- G shear modulus of masonry
- c wall stress coefficient (1.2 in the case of symmetric and 0.3 in the case of cantilever boundary conditions)

For unstrengthened wall (pier) elements, the resistance to horizontal loads ($V_{P,URM}$) is the lowest value between bending ($V_{P,f,URM}$) and shear resistance ($V_{P,d,URM}$), which are determined through Eqs. 3.10 and 3.11, respectively:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \min(V_{P,f(URM)}; V_{P,d(URM)}) \quad (3.9)$$

$$V_{P,f(URM)} = \frac{\sigma_0 \cdot t \cdot I_p^2}{2 \cdot \alpha \cdot h} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{f_m} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = A_w \frac{f_t}{\beta} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{f_t}} \quad (3.11)$$

Where:

- t masonry wall/pier thickness
- σ_0 mean compressive stress on the wall
- α stress coefficient for the bending moment (0.5 for symmetric and 1.0 for the cantilever boundary conditions)
- f_m masonry vertical compressive strength
- f_t masonry referential diagonal tensile strength
- β shear stress distribution factor in the wall (h/l but between 1,5 and 1,0)

From the idealized load capacity of the wall and its initial stiffness, the displacement at the elastic limit is obtained. The ultimate displacement (rotation) of the wall for shear and bending failure mechanisms is defined in the input data.

For the in-plane shear mechanism, the software considers the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12]. For the in-plane bending mechanism of piers, the software accounts only for the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads.

According to the EC8 standard, the total ultimate transverse force due to an earthquake (ultimate base shear coefficient) is determined as follows:

$$BSC_u = \gamma_I \cdot a_{gR} \cdot S \cdot \frac{2.5}{q} \quad (3.12)$$

where:

- γ_I Importance factor
- a_{gR} reference peak ground acceleration
- S soil factor
- q structural behaviour factor

The storey resistance (SRC) is defined as the ultimate load capacity of the storey divided by the weight of the building above it. This coefficient (SRC) must be greater than the seismic load coefficient (BSC) calculated according to the EC8-1 standard:

$$BSC \leq SRC \quad \text{or} \quad E_d \leq R_d \quad (3.13)$$

In addition to the load capacity, the critical storey must also have sufficient ductility, which is determined from the structural behaviour factor (q). This factor reduces the force based on the ability of the structure to inelastically absorb the seismic load by means of hysteretic damping.

The calculated idealized ductility of the critical floor (μ) must be greater than the ultimate ductility (μ_u).

$$\mu_u = \frac{q^2 + 1}{2} \quad (3.14)$$

with:

$$\mu_u \leq \mu$$

Once the input data are provided, the user runs the program (written in Matlab/Octave), and the results are presented graphically (Fig. 3.4.2) and stored in output files.

Fig. 3.4.2 Results of SREMB :storey envelopes for push-over in one direction and 3D representation of elements near failure – coloured by utilization

3.4.3. How to account for CRM

SREMB implements equations for calculating strength of masonry elements strengthened with FRM, accordingly to CNR-DT 215/2018 [15]. The user defines appropriate material data to account for the CRM in the input Excel file (Fig. 3.4.3) and also increases ultimate drift limits.

n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)	način	E [MPa]	G [MPa]	fc [MPa]	ft [MPa]	du.s [-]	du.f [-]
Pilot_01								
5	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
6	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
7	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
8	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02

		način računa	vnos karakteristik za FRCM - CRN-DT 215:2018												
n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)		splošni koef.	tau.0 [MPa]	gama.Rd	n.f	t.vf [mm]	l.f [m]	d.t [m]	alfa.t	E.f.d [MPa]	eps.fd [mm/m]	eps.mu [mm/m]		
5	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	1,65	2,25	1	72700	18,5	35		
6	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	2,5	2,50	1	72700	18,5	35		
7	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	0,25	0,25	1	72700	18,5	35		
8	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	0,25	0,25	1	72700	18,5	35		

Fig. 3.4.3 Input data for CRM

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References

- [1] Paulay T, Priestly MJN. Seismic Design of Reinforced Concrete and Masonry Buildings. 1st ed. Wiley; 1992. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470172841>.
- [2] Tomažević M. Earthquake-Resistant Design of Masonry Buildings. vol. 1. Imperial College Press; 1999.
- [3] Hendry AW. Structural masonry. Basingstoke: Macmillan Press; 1990.
- [4] Magenes G, Calvi GM. In-plane seismic response of brick masonry walls. Earthq Eng Struct Dyn 1997;26:1091–112.::AID-EQE693>3.0.CO;2-6.
- [5] Gattesco N, Boem I, Rizzi E, Gams M. PRO-SIS Report 1.1: Design analytical models 2024.
- [6] Tomažević M. The computer program POR. Rep ZRMK 1978;846.
- [7] Magenes G, Della Fontana A. Simplified non-linear seismic analysis of masonry buildings, 1998, p. 190–5.
- [8] Roca P, Molins C, Marí AR. Strength Capacity of Masonry Wall Structures by the Equivalent Frame Method. J Struct Eng 2005;131:1601–10. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2005\)131:10\(1601\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2005)131:10(1601)).
- [9] Lagomarsino S, Penna A, Galasco A, Cattari S. TREMURI program: An equivalent frame model for the nonlinear seismic analysis of masonry buildings. Eng Struct 2013;56:1787–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2013.08.002>.

- [10] Caliò I, Marletta M, Pantò B. A new discrete element model for the evaluation of the seismic behaviour of unreinforced masonry buildings. Eng Struct 2012;40:327–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2012.02.039>.
- [11] Gen 2023 Manual n.d. <https://manual.midasuser.com/KR/Gen/935/whnjs.htm>.
- [12] Turnšek V, Čačovič F. Some experimental results on the strength of brick masonry walls. Proc 2nd Int Brick Mason Conf Stoke--Trent 1971:149–56.
- [13] Federal Emergency Management Agency. ATC FEMA 356: Prestandard and commentary for the seismic rehabilitation of buildings. 2000.
- [14] 3muri User Manual, Version: 12.6.1 n.d. http://www.stadata.com/Aggiornamenti/3Muri/manuali/3Muri12.6.1_ENG.zip.
- [15] CNR DT 215/2018 Guide for the Design and Construction of Externally Bonded Fibre Reinforced Inorganic Matrix Systems for Strengthening Existing Structures.
- [16] https://www.2si.it/it/2024/10/29/rilasciato-pro_sap-24-10-0/
- [17] https://www.2si.it/en/pro_sam_eng/
- [18] MIT - Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti. Aggiornamento delle «Norme tecniche per le costruzioni». Decreto 17 gennaio 2018.
- [19] MIT - Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti. Circolare 21 gennaio 2019, n. 7 C.S.LL.PP.: Istruzioni per l'applicazione dell'«Aggiornamento delle “Norme tecniche per le costruzioni”» di cui al decreto ministeriale 17 gennaio 2018. 2019

Appendix A.

The “Equivalent frame” model for masonry buildings

The “Equivalent frame” method [17] for the modelling of masonry walls and structures basically consists in schematizing the structure into an equivalent frame system composed of vertical and horizontal resisting structural macro-elements (i.e. the piers and the spandrels) connected by means of rigid nodes (Fig. A 1a). Each macro-element is represented as a beam element along its principal centroid axis, with nodes positioned at the intersections with the centroid axes of the orthogonal connected elements. Infinitely rigid segments at the ends of the masonry macro-elements allow to model the reduced deformability of the structural nodes.

The length of the deformable part of a pier, i.e. the effective length l_{eff} , can be calculated by applying Eq. (A.1):

$$l_{eff} = l' + \frac{b(H - l')}{3l'} \leq H \quad (A.1)$$

being l' the conventional length determined accordingly to Fig. A 1b, b the pier width, H the net interstorey height. The effective deformable portion is located proportionally to the length of the lower and upper rigid parts, as specified by Eq. A.2.

$$l_{inf,eff} = l_{inf} \left(1 - \frac{l_{eff} - l'}{l_{inf} + l_{sup}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad l_{sup,eff} = l_{sup} \left(1 - \frac{l_{eff} - l'}{l_{inf} + l_{sup}} \right) \quad (A.2)$$

being, l_{inf} and l_{sup} the conventional length of the lower and upper rigid parts of the vertical element ($l_{inf} + l' + l_{sup} = H$).

The elastic deformation of the structural elements depends on the elasticity of the beam elements, while the inelastic response is lumped in rotational and shear plastic hinges. The rotational plastic hinges at the ends of the beam elements simulate the inelastic in-plane bending response, while the shear plastic hinge at mid-length represents the inelastic in-plane shear response.

Fig. A 1 Modelling of a masonry wall according to the Equivalent frame method (a), definition of the effective pier length (b), and location of the lumped plasticity hinges (c)

Appendix B.

Analytical calculations for validation

The numerical models are validated with reference to a pier and a spandrel element, represented in Fig. 3.4.1. The masonry and CRM characteristics adopted are reported in Table B.1. The pier is subjected to a vertical stress of 0.3 MPa and both the shear-type (*st*) and the cantilever (*ct*) beam static schemes are considered. The spandrel is assumed to have an effective horizontal steel tie. The main parameters assumed in the calculations are those collected in Table B.1.

Fig. 3.4.1 Benchmark examples: (a) pier and (b) spandrel elements (measures in mm)

Table B.1: Main characteristics for the benchmark examples.

ID	Value	Unit	Description
t_m	250	mm	masonry thickness
b'	800	mm	net masonry spandrel height (typically, lintel is not considered)
E_m	1500	MPa	secant Young's modulus of masonry
G_m	500	MPa	shear modulus of masonry ($E_m/3$)
f_m	3.45	MPa	vertical compressive strength
$f_{m,h}$	1.725	MPa	horizontal compressive strength ($f_m/2$)
τ_0	0.09	MPa	equivalent masonry shear strength under zero vertical stress
H_p	100	kN	resistance of the horizontal tie of the spandrel
T_G	5.11	kN	tensile resistance of a GFRP wire.
s	66	mm	GFRP mesh grid pitch
t_c	30	mm	mortar coating thickness
E_c	10000	MPa	secant Young's modulus of the coating mortar
H_p	100	kN	tensile resistance of the horizontal steel tie

To schematize analytically, in a simplified way, the in-plane lateral performances of masonry piers and spandrels, an elastic-plastic behaviour is considered. To estimate the stiffness, resistance and ultimate displacement capacities, the analytical correlations presented in [5] are adopted. Note that, in case of spandrels provided with both effective horizontal tie and CRM, in the correlation for the bending resistance it is assumed $\sigma_0 = H_p/(b't)$, considering both tensile failure of the mesh and crushing of the masonry as potential failure modes.

Table B.2: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark pier (shear-type scheme).

Pier_st_0.3		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_m	[MPa]	3.45	3.45	3.45
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	42.7	80.9	119.0
x	[mm]	-	195.1	248.3
M_p	[kNm]	52.6	84.8	112.6
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	56.1	90.4	120.1
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	50.5	98.9	147.3
V_p	[kN]	50.5	90.4	120.1
Mode	[-]	Diag. cracking	Bending	Bending
$d_{p,e}$	[mm]	1.18	1.18	1.08
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	9.4	37.5	37.5

Table B.3: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark pier (cantilever beam scheme)

Pier_ct_0.3		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_m	[MPa]	3.45	3.45	3.45
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	19.8	36.5	53.2
x	[mm]	-	195.1	248.3
M_p	[kNm]	52.6	84.8	112.6
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	22.2	35.8	47.6
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	50.5	98.9	147.3
V_p	[kN]	22.2	35.8	47.6
Mode	[-]	Bending	Bending	Bending
$d_{p,e}$	[mm]	1.12	1.00	0.92
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	18.8	37.5	37.5

Table B.4: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark spandrel.

Spandrel		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_{hd}	[MPa]	1.73	1.73	1.73
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	66.9	128.1	189.1
x	[mm]	-	301.0	309.7
M_s	[kNm]	26.4	29.0*	29.5*
$V_{s,f}$	[kN]	43.9	48.4	49.2
$V_{s,d}$	[kN]	18.0	41.8	72.7
$V'_{s,d}$	[kN]	10.8	-	-
V_s	[kN]	18.0	41.8	49.2
Mode	[-]	Diag. cracking	Diag. cracking	Bending
$d_{s,e}$	[mm]	0.27	0.21	0.26
$d_{s,u}$	[mm]	6.0	36.0	36.0

* In both reinforced configurations, bending failure occurs due to masonry crushing, so the R2 configuration results in only a slight increase in the bending resistance in respect to the R1 configuration.

Legend:

- i number of CRM-strengthened sides (1-2)
- χ effectiveness reduction factor (=1 for CRM at both-sides, ≤ 1 at one side)
- K_e elastic stiffness
- x depth of the neutral axis of the cracked cross-section
- M resisting bending moment
- V_f in-plane lateral resistance related to bending mechanism
- V_d in-plane lateral resistance related to diagonal cracking mechanism
- V in-plane lateral resistance
- d_e yield displacement
- d_u ultimate displacement